

Ìjọ Àdìmúlà (An Institutionalised Indigenous Religious Movement in Yorubaland)

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Entry tags: Religious Group, African Religions, Yoruba Language, Yoruba Religions, African Religion, Language

Ìjọ Àdìmúlà is a unified movement of Yoruba traditional religion that sprung up in Ile-Ife under the leadership of Olorunfemi Osiiga an Ìjèbú man in the 1920s. The term Ìjọ means assembly while Àdìmúlà means "The Personality one can hold on to and be saved". The term has been adopted to describe Yoruba religion. Ìjọ Àdìmúlà started as a secessionist movement from Ìjọ Àdìmúlà ti Kírstì (which was a Christian denomination). It was noted that Osiiga's goal was to create a purely Yoruba traditional religious worship system which has since spread to other Yoruba communities of southwestern, Nigeria. Ìjọ Àdìmúlà came into existence in some other communities as a need for social coercion for members of Yoruba indigenous religion. It was noted that the prevalence of Christianity in those communities was gradually driving indigenous religion into extinction which calls for a drastic reaction from practitioners of indigenous religion to have a voice. Such communities include Ọlà, Màsífà, Òkò, Èjìgbò, Òsogbo, among others. Ìjọ Àdìmúlà gained more prominence in Ilé-Ife, Ọlà, Màsífà, and several others within Osun State. The membership of the group is drawn from every Yoruba religious group such as Ifá, Sàngó, Ọya, Egúngún, Ògún, and Obàtálá among others. The group population varies from one community to the other. For instance, Ilé-Ife has an average population of 220, Ọlà 750, and Màsífà 630 with women and children inclusive. Some of the distinctive features of Ìjọ Àdìmúlà to the different Yoruba religious groups are the creation of structures within the system, the use of documented text that has unarguably been associated with Yoruba indigenous religion, and the introduction of public service within modernised buildings called Ilé Ìjùbà (worship centres) as opposed to worship in shrines and groves. It is important to note that the temple is regarded as a sacred place where the divinities abide, because of this notion reference is accorded to the temple demonstrated by individual putting off their shoes before entering into the temple. Also individuals bow themselves touching the floor with their forehead in reverence to the divinities believed to be present in the temple. The group structures comprise both administrative and spiritual: the administrative includes alàgbà tàbí Awon Agbàgbà Ìjọ (Elders), Igbimò Ìjọ (Council of the assembly), Awon Akowé Ìjọ (Secretaries and Treasurers of the Assembly), Egbẹ Amú Ìjọ dùn (which they interpreted as Deacons and Deaconess), Egbẹ Qdẹ (Security); while the spiritual involves Adarí Ìjọ/Olorí Ìjọ (Leader of the Assembly), Asọse Ìjọ (Preacher), Awon Egbẹ Akorin Ifágbayé, Ifálólayọ, Odòdó/Ìràwò Ọrúnmilà (Choir groups for married women, single ladies and the children respectively who dress in their different regalia), among others. The group days of worship differ from one community to the other. It was gathered that Ìjọ Àdìmúlà in Ilé-Ife worship on Sunday while those in Màsífà and Ọlà worship on Saturday. The form of worship was purely liturgical although it allows for a bit of flexibility. The leading personnel reads from the worship guide while the congregation listens and responds at the appropriate places. The content of the worship guide begins with a call to worship, then a processional hymn, and salutations to Olódùmarè, followed by other òrìsà of Yoruba which includes all deities and Orí (destiny) which is often regarded as one of the most important personal òrìsà among the Yoruba. This is followed by Ìwúre Ìbẹẹre Ìsìn (Opening prayer) and other features such as Ọrọ Ìwúrí (sermon), Ìdávó (collection of plates), Ìdúpe (thanksgiving), Orin láti ọdọ Awon Akorin (choir renditions) among others. It should be noted that Ifá corpus that are documented in the worship guide forms the major text of every sermon, however, the preacher is at liberty to recite any Odù Ifá (Ifa verse) he or she deems necessary for his sermon and close the service with a congregational prayer. The group in each community also has àjòdún which is specific annual festival that they hold in high esteem.

Date Range: 1920 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Osun

Region tags: Western Africa, Ile-Ife, Ola, Masifa, Osun State, Nigeria, Africa

Ile-Ife the cradle of Yoruba Race, Ola, and Masifa are prominent ancients Yoruba communities in the 19th century

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Ogungbile, David O. "The Dynamics of Language in Cultural Revolution and African Spirituality: The Case of Ijo Orile-Ede Adulawo Ti Kristi (National Church of Christ) in Nigeria." *Nordic Journal of African Studies* 10(1): 66-79 (2001)
- Source 2: Elesemoyo, Ebenezer O. Elements, Forms, and Structure of Ijo Adimùlà in Selected Yoruba Communities of Southwestern Nigeria. A Thesis Written in the Department of Religious Studies, Faculty of Arts and Submitted to the Postgraduate College, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria, in Partial Fulfilment of the Requirements for the Award of the Degree of Master of Arts in Religious Studies M. A. Thesis, 2023
- Source 3: Afolábí, Gàniyù Adébáyò. Itúpalè Lítírèsò Ifá Ninú Ìjòsin Àwon Ìjo Àdimùlà (An Analysis of Ifá Literature in The Worship of Ijo Adimùlà). A Thesis Written in the Department of Linguistic and African Languages, Faculty of Arts and Submitted to the Postgraduate College, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria, in Partial Fulfilment of the Requirements for the Award of the Degree of Master of Arts in Religious Studies M. A. Thesis , 2012.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.facebook.com/babalawoifaponmile.irosunagbe/videos/2179202792423232>

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://fb.watch/r1zWPFSA6T/>
- Source 1 Description: Link to worship of Ijo Adimula in Oko town. The video presents Ijo Adimula during a special worship service. The worship also featured an award presentation to deserving personalities.
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.facebook.com/100068886702028/videos/2179202792423232/>
- Source 2 Description: Link to Facebook video of Ijo Adimula Ola town. The video features Ijo Adimula 1 temple during a worship session. In the video we see one of the leaders chanting an oral verse to call congregants to service. This chant (call to worship) is the first item in the order of programmes in most Ijo Adimula in Osun State, Nigeria.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Other religious groups are visible within the community. The influence of the other religious groups (especially Islam and Christianity) with which the Ijo Adimula relates could be seen in the groups adoption of worship styles and structure similar with the groups mentioned above. It is therefore safe to conclude that they have cultural contact with other cultural group.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: The cultural contact is very competitive in nature as it seeks to dominate the region

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– No

Notes: The opposing cultural view considers itself superior to the indigenous one

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: there has been conflict in the past which resulted to the establishment of schools by the indigenous worshipers to protect their wards

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not have a special process or system for assigning religious affiliation. Anyone and everyone who feels persuaded about the group can join voluntarily.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: The religious group's goal is to maintain her members. However, people who seek the intervention of the Ijo Adimula religious specialists during life's crisis often pledge their loyalty to the group and thus become permanent members of the group. They do this to continue to enjoy further protection or as a mark of appreciation to the group.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 1600

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 5

Notes: The percentage in Masifa and Ola are as high as 70-75 of the entire population, but significantly low in Ile-Ife

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (actively discouraged-suppressed by larger religious group(s))

Notes: The group serves as an umbrella body for adherents of Yoruba indigenous religions in the study region. The group does not prevent other religious groups from practicing their faith so long they do not attack their faith or their members.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: There are prominent individuals among the group. These individuals occupy important positions in the traditional leadership of the community. A good number of them are local chiefs in the community/kingdom.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: The hierarchy among leaders is spelt out in the following manner. There are two criteria by which a member's status is determined in this group. One is the prominence of an individual within the larger community. For example, a local chief within the community is usually accorded much respect and given prominence in the group. This is because such an individual is usually versed and vast in the indigenous religious traditions of their community. The other criterion has to do with the individual's prominence within the group. For example, some folks do give themselves to searching out and gaining mastery of the art and act of worship of the local deity in their community. Such individuals are accorded respect and a status based on their knowledge of the religion.

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– No

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

Notes: In cases where Ijo Adimula comprises adherents of a variety of Yoruba traditional religions/deities, the leaders of each autonomous group are acknowledged and treated as leaders within the umbrella group (Ijo Adimula) in their local community.

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– No

Notes: Ijo Adimula does not operate a regional leadership structure. Each Ijo Adimula is independent of the other although they can work together to achieve a common goal. However, no local group is subordinate to another.

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

Notes: Ijo Adimula does not have such structure.

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

Notes: Apart from each community having its own council, there is no other council overseeing the local ones.

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 1

Notes: Just the local ones

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

Notes: just that they have a good understanding of the faith and of good character which can also be possessed by members of the group.

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– No

Notes: It's the group council that decides who becomes what.

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– No

Notes: The leaders of the group do not have ministers who are loyal to them at the expense of the group other than the usual members of the council and individuals occupying different offices within the group. Each member of the council works in the overall interest of the group as there are consequences for divided loyalty to their deities.

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– Yes

Notes: Being the ones who sit at the council, it is safe to say they appoint the leader

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

Notes: The group is hardly influenced by politicians. In fact, not on the ground that an individual has the backing of politician(s)

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– No

Notes: By the council

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– No

Notes: Not necessary, that can only be done in extreme cases where they couldn't adjudge the personality of those available.

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– Yes

Notes: The leaders are humans, therefore the group believes they can fall.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– No

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Notes: The members of the congregation are giving the opportunity to declare their acceptance and rejection of whoever is being considered as the leader of the group without intimidation.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: They have verses of the Ifa corpus collected and printed into single document for the purpose of worship. However, these Ifa verses are not exhaustive. They are just a minute portion of the general Ifa verses passed on from generations past.

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: They also refer to oral traditions and other Ifa verses not included in the worship guide.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Notes: Although they have variations due to multiple dialect that has characterised Yoruba language.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, these individuals learn as apprentices from priests and/or priestesses and are found knowledgeable before they can be assigned as leaders within the group.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The collected Ifa verses serve as her canon of scriptures.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: There are a good number of monumental religious architecture acknowledged and preserved by the group.

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage: 5

Notes: There are several religious monuments within the communities. However, most of the land in these communities are deployed for farming and other agricultural activities. This limits the percentage of landmass reserved for religious monuments.

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 220

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Height, square meters: 200

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage of area: 5

Notes: Ile-Ife which happens to be the largest settlement is highly populated with religious monuments and the presence of shrines, altars traditional worship centres..

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– No

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: The group has temples they referred to as Ile Ijuba (worship centres)

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Notes: There are altars where sacrifices are made. most of these altars are not elevated spots. another type of altar is located within worship centers. These are places where the leading minister sits during worship.

↳ Devotional markers:

– No

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: There are grooves and shrines that have been dedicated to different deities or historical figures (deified ancestors) where people gather for worship and other social and cultural purposes.

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Grooves

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

- On persons
- At home
- Only religious public space
- Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Notes: There are a good number of them with symbols associated with deities. These are found in the worship centres and homes of devotees, especially the votaries of the various deities.

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– No

↳ Humans:

– Yes

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: animals, plants, and historic figures

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: All the deities and some historic figures have one sacred site or the other. e.g. Obatala groove, Oranmiyan groove etc.

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: Due to sacredness ascribed to such spaces they are often protected with trees which serve to also protect the cosmos.

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: Even though these sites are often visited by strangers and adherents, visiting does not constitute an important milestone in the belief of the group.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: The group acknowledges that the body is distinct from the spirit but both must be present for the human being to exist.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds the belief that the spirit is as the wind, which though is invisible, intangible and abstract but nonetheless, real and active.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: Spirit possession. e.g. The elegun Sango will have to be possessed by Sango spirit before performance.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes the human soul (especially those who lived a good life while on earth) lives in another realm called ancestors world after death.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes believes that the soul of the dead return to the world in a circle. Some into the same family as a new child and some to other families.

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form:

– Yes

Notes: This is not the norm. However, it does happen.

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– Yes

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– Yes

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– Yes

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– Yes [specify]: The group believes one may reincarnate to live in a very distant location from his/her initial base to fulfil destiny if the person died untimely in their first sojourn on earth.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– No

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifices present:

– No

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– Yes [specify]: properties the deceased held in high esteem. This could be instruments or tools the individual used while on earth.

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Notes: Religious objects consider to be personal to such individual. some of such object could be inform of wristband or necklace.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Notes: If the deceased was very high-ranking personnel within the group, such as the King, there are specific tomb-crypt where they must be buried.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: If member happened to be a king, he has to be buried in a designated site for kings after series of rite has been performed.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes in Olodumare as the Supreme God who create and governs the universe through the aid of his subordinates who serve as intermediaries between the Supreme Being and the world and man.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: Creator God, Omniscient, god of Justice etc.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high God is conceived as one who sees the inner thoughts of humans. He is said to be fully aware of human thoughts and contemplations.

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high God is conceived as one who sees the inner thoughts of humans. He is said to be fully aware of human thoughts and contemplations.

- ↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
 - Yes [specify]: he is considered to be Omniscient.
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Depending on the kind of response the actions of humans deserve from him
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Because they are means to the supreme high god, and not end in themselves
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Creator god and Omnibenevolent

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: Through his subordinates

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Through intermediaries

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Through possession of other humans or object or dreams and trance

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

- ↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - No
 - ↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):
 - No
 - ↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - No
 - ↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
 - Yes [specify]: Could perceive an upcoming danger and warn the living
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: anger

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination processes:

– Yes

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– Yes [specify]: Possession of other being

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: If they want to allow themselves to be seen, they could make it possible. They could also possess a human or object to be seen.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Notes: They often have their area of dominance

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
 - Yes [specify]: This is the reason they are often consulted when faced with certain situations
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: anger and appeasement.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have other knowledge of the human world:

– Yes [specify]: Their knowledge of the world is not inexhaustive. Though they have some knowledge which the living members of the world do not have, however, they do not have all the knowledge that there is in the world.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can punish:
– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:
– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:
– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:
– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
– Yes [specify]: thirst

↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Yes

↳ In dreams:
– Yes

↳ In trance possession:
– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:
– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:
– Yes

Notes: Most times through specialist

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: could also communicate through the natural environment, such as trees, rivers etc.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– No

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Yes [specify]: Deities include Obatala, Orunmila, Ogun, Sango, Esu, etc.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that the Supreme Being through the intermediaries monitor everything that happens on earth. It believes that the Supreme Being assigns areas of dominance to each of the deities and they give account back to him on matters that concerns their territory. It is believed that there are deities in charge of the waters, the air, thunder, farmland, sacrifice, among others. Human conducts are also monitored and rewarded accordingly.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– Yes

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Time and season also matters to them

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
– Yes [specify]: charity

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that Olodumare gave the divinities the power to reward and punish human accordingly. it also believes that these divinities have the power to harm human if they are not appeased.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:
– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:
– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]
– Yes

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:
– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: This depends on how the deceased lived while on earth

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: Dependent on the kind of life lived by the deceased

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Could also result to reincarnation into lesser beings or object

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: sudden misfortune

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes the supernatural beings have the capacity as bestowed on them by Olodumare (The Supreme Being). This is the reason they often consult and made sacrifice to appease these being. The rewards can be here on earth and also can be in the afterlife.

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes

- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - Yes

- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes

- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
 - Yes

- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
 - Yes

- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
 - Yes

- ↳ Other [specify]
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
 - Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - Yes

- ↳

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - Yes
 - Notes: longlife

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: Although the group believes Olodumare sent his only son Ella to this world. The believe is that Ella is to come and repair and restore order to the world.

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: The believe of the group is that each individual will die and get their reward in the afterlife or continue to reincarnate in endless cycles. They do not belief that there is a complete end to this world.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The group lays much emphasis on moral living. For the group, determinant of the reward in the afterlife is quality if the moral life lived on earth.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes in wholeness, that is being complete in living and uprightness.

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation:
 - Yes
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
 - Yes
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
 - Yes
- ↳ Strength (physical):
 - Yes

- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
 - Yes
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
 - Yes
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
 - Yes

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: Hospitality

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: In their religious beliefs, the group places emphasis on procreation as one of the major determinants of successful living.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– No

Notes: The religious group allows men have multiple wives

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Notes: The group beliefs that women should not be married to more than one man at a time.

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: The group does not encourage extra marital affairs among men. It is more desirable for a man to have multiples wives than being involved with women whom he is not married to.

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: The group does not promote pre-marital and extra-marital affairs among women. Lesbianism is also not to be contemplated among woman as homosexuality is also not to be practiced by men.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: castration is unacceptable by the group. It is considered inhumane.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: fasting can be prescribed for an individual going through certain procedure for a breakthrough. But not a requirement for membership neither is it prescribed for the congregation.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Notes: Although an individual or adherent of certain deities might have some. E.g. Adherent of Obatala do not take palm wine. This does not become a taboo for the entire group.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: The group does not indulge in human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: They do not indulge in human sacrifice

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: suicide is considered an abomination. In fact, whoever commit suicide cannot be buried unless certain cleansing sacrifices are performed to ward off evil from the family.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: The group encourages consistent attendance in service with the belief that Olodumare count on it

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Notes: The group encouraged its members to be careful and not be negligent in any situation.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Notes: members are encouraged to live up to expectations, but not a prerequisite.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: The group has for a long time experienced marginalisation, however, it encourages its members to place humanity ahead of everything and that they should not dissociate themselves from others.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: While individual might have reason to perform rituals, membership of the group is open to all without any form of rituals. Also in periods of life crisis, individual members consult with priests and other religious specialists to carry out sacrifices or rituals which are believed upon to be potent to solve their problems and restore calmness or normalcy to their situations.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Notes: This includes annual or periodic rituals, festivals, ceremonies and other celebrations.

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 200

Notes: This figure may include spectators and lovers of the adherents who are carrying out their religious duties. Such spectators attend the events in solidarity with their family and friends.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 10

Notes: This depends on some factors. Some festivals and ceremonies that are held over a number of days. However, some important festivals hold annually.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Yes

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: This creates a sense of identity, affinity and belonging among them. It is widely used and common among the group.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A tribe

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: When the group discovered an intentional move by other religious institutions to indoctrinate her young members in the elementary school established by those religious institutions, it withdrew its members and went ahead to establish its own, to protect its interest.

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Notes: The group encourages whoever is willing to pursue education to the peak of their potential..

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: The group established schools for the purpose of their entire community

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: There are educational institutions established by other institutions that can be attended by members of the group. However, the schools often serve as means of evangelism and as a result to draw away the members of the group.

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: There is no formal bureaucracy. The group encourages flexibility within its structure to encourage active participation of all.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: They interact with the government through its agencies and organs set up to administer the country.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: By the government

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The state police have jurisdiction over the region and therefore oversees all matters that deserves its attention.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: Such authority is not conferred on the group. At best the group has elders and the traditional kingship system who can mediate on matters of concern.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The region is under the jurisdiction of the state judicial system.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: The group does not have institutionalised punishment, since it does not have institutionalised judges or judicial system.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Because they live and operate within the jurisdiction of an institutionalised legal system, they are bound by the system and whatever punishment given to them if found culpable of any misconduct.

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: A possibility depending on the crime committed.

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Notes: The state does not send its citizen on exile.

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: Especially if the property is discovered to be acquired through embezzlement of public funds, such property could be forfeited.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: It operates within the legal code of the state.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Legal code of the state

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group has members who serve in the nation's military.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Being a resident of the state, they are protected by the state's military.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: Yoruba is the regional language. All communications and chants are encoded in Yoruba language.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: They employ the state's calendar.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The group sources for and farms to meet their food consumption needs.

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